

Selection of best lines and hybrids on the basis of genetic variability analysis in Maize (*Zea mays* L.)

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on Jan 08, 2020 Revised on Feb 04, 2020 Accepted on Feb 15, 2020 Published on March 03, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Ankit Kumar, Amit Tomar Corresponding Author Email ankitjayni@gmail.com</p>	<p>The results revealed that parents namely, TSK-10, TSK-27, New Blue-II, Kurara and TSK-109 were found highly genetic diverse for days to 50% tasseling, days to 50% silking, days to 755 dry husk. The parents namely, TSK-109, Kurara, New Blue-II and TSK-10 were found highly genetic diverse for plant height (cm), cob height, number of cobs per plant and number of grains per cob. The parents namely, Kurara, TSK-109, TSK-10, New Blue-II and TSK-27 were found highly genetic diverse for shelling percentage, grain yield per plant, grain yield per cob and 100-grain weight.</p>
PUBLICATION INFO	KEYWORDS
<p>International Journal of Agricultural Invention (IJAI) RNI: UPENG/2016/70091 ISSN: 2456-1797 (P) Vol.: 5, Issue: 1, Pages: 45-49 Journal Homepage URL http://agriinventionjournal.com/ DOI: 10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.6</p>	<p>Diallel Mating Design, Genetic Variability, Maize, Mean Effect</p>

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Kumar, A., Tomar, A. (2020) Selection of best lines and hybrids on the basis of genetic variability analysis in Maize (*Zea mays* L.), *International Journal of Agricultural Invention*, 5(1): 45-49. DOI: [10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.6](https://doi.org/10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.6)

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is third most important cereal crop of the world after wheat and rice. It belongs to grass family and important to human being because of their role as staple food in many areas of the world. It is also used to produce animal feed, oils, starch, flour, sugar, syrup, processed foods, malt, alcoholic beverages and renewable energy. Approximately 50% of the world's calories are provided by rice, wheat and maize, but in many parts of Africa and Asia, people really depends on grains such as sorghum or millet. Maize is also utilized in USA in brewing industry and ethanol production. The primary centre of origin of maize is Central America and Mexico. The studies indicated that maize was important crop in Mexico about 5000 year ago or perhaps earlier.

American Indian grew and selectively improved maize from 3400 BC to 1500 AD. Maize was first grown in Europe then spread in Spain later on it spread from Spain to southern France and Italy. In India it introduced probably in the beginning of seventeenth century. Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is also called “The queen of cereals” which includes eight genera, five of these (*Coix*, *Schlerachne*, *Polytoca*, *Chinonachne* and *Trilobachene*) are relatively unimportant while the three as important American genera are: *Zea*, *Tripsacum* and *Euchalaena* (Teosinte). Five species of genus *Zea* viz, *maxicana*, *perennis*, *laxurian*, *diploperenis* and *mays*. First four species are wild and commonly called Teosinte and the last species *Zea mays* is only cultivated.

The diploid chromosome number of maize is 20. The wild species *Z. perennis* is tetraploid ($4n=40$) rest are diploid. On the basis of kernel characteristics maize are classified in different groups (Kipps-1959) viz., *Z. mays everta* (pop corn), *Z. mays saccharata* (sweet corn), *Z. mays amylacea* (soft corn), *Z. mays tunicata* (pod corn) and *Z. mays cerantinakulesh* (waxy corn).

Materials and Methods

An experiment was carried out at Oilseed Research Farm, Kalyanpur of C.S.A. University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur during *rabi* 2017-18. Experimental material consisting 45 genotypes (9 parents namely; CIM 78, KURARA, TSK 109, TSK 36, TSK 92, TSK 27, HK1-193-1, TSK 10 and NEW BLUE II and their possible 36 F_1 s crosses, were developed by using diallel mating design excluding reciprocal) were evaluated in three replication using Randomized Block Design (RBD) for 13 traits namely; days to 50% tasseling, days to 50% silking, days to 75% dry husk, plant height, cob height, no. of cobs/plant, no. of grain rows/cob, no. of grains/row, cob weight, 100-grain weight, grain yield/cob, grain yield/plant and shelling percentage. Each parent and cross was planted in 5 m single row length spaced at 60 x 25 cm between rows and plants, respectively.

All the recommended package of practices were adopted according to the recommended by agronomical practices.

Results and Discussion

The mean, range and variability in parents and F_1 s for 13 characters are presented in Table-1. The results obtained for these parameters are described as below:

Days to 50 % Teaseling

The parents and F_1 s mean variability ranged from 85 (TSK 10) to 90.33 (TSK 27) days and 82.33 (KURARA x TSK 10) to 88.33 (CIM 78 x TSK 10) days, respectively. The mean values were 88.04 and 84.89 for parents and F_1 s, respectively.

Days to 50% Silking

Among the parents, the variability ranged from 88.66 (TSK 10) to 93.66 (TSK 109) days and

for F_1 s 85.66 (TSK 27 x NEW BLUE II) to 92.33 (CIM 78 x HK1-193-1, CIM 78x TSK 10) days. Mean of Parents and F_1 s values were 91.56 and 88.73 days, respectively.

Days to 75 % Dry Husk

The variability among the parents ranged from 130.66 (TSK 27) to 139.67 (TSK 10) days and for F_1 s 125.33 (HK1-193-1 x NEW BLUE II) to 138.33 (TSK 92 x TSK 27) days. Parents and F_1 s mean values were 136.37 and 130.75 days, respectively.

Plant Height (cm)

Among the parents, the variability ranged from 140.33 (TSK 10) to 161.34 (CIM 78) cm and among the crosses, it ranged from 130.00 (TSK 10 x NEW BLUE II) to 163.33 (KURARA x NEW BLUE II) cm. The means for parents and F_1 s were 147.85 and 146.57 cm, respectively. Similar findings were also observed by (Abirami *et al.*, 2005, Appunu *et al.*, 2006, Alaminie *et al.*, 2006, Akhanda *et al.*, 2007, Asif *et al.*, 2010, Anshuman *et al.*, 2013 and Abdel-Moneam *et al.*, 2014).

Cob Height (cm)

The range observed among parents varied from 68.66 (HK1-193-1) to 75.33 (KURARA) and among F_1 s from 57.66 (TSK 109 x TSK 10) to 79.66 (CIM 78 x HK1-193-1) cm. The mean values for parents and F_1 s were 71.44 to 69.59 cm, respectively.

Number of Cobs per Plant

The average number of cobs per plant among parents varied from 1.11 (TSK 27, HK1-193-1, TSK 10) to 1.25 (CIM 78, KURARA) where as among crosses it varied from 1.00 (KURARA x NEW BLUE II, KURARA x TSK 27, TSK 36 x TSK 92, TSK 92 x NEW BLUE II) to 1.36 (CIM 78 x TSK 92). The mean values for the parents and crosses were 1.16 to 1.15, respectively.

Cob Weight (g)

The range observed among parents varied from 83.14(TSK 109) to 121.83 (CIM 78) and among F_1 s from 107.33 (KURARA x TSK 36) to

152.19 (KURARA x NEW BLUE II). The mean values for parents and F₁s were 99.86 and 126.42g, respectively.

Number of Grain Rows per Cob

Among the parents, the variability ranged from 12.11 (TSK 92) to 13.53 (CIM 78, KURARA, TSK 109) and for F₁s 12.88 (TSK 36 x TSK 92, TSK 36 x TSK 27, TSK 92 x HK1-193-1, HK1-193-

1 x TSK 10) to 15.55 (CIM 78 x TSK 92, KURARA x NEW BLUE II, TSK 27 x TSK 10). Parents and F₁s mean values were 13.07 and 13.98, respectively. These findings were similar to (Katna, *et al.*, 2005, Hemavashy *et al.*, 2008, Chauhan *et al.*, 2010, Kashi *et al.*, 2010, Jawaharlal *et al.*, 2011, Gautam *et al.*, 2011, Lal *et al.*, 2012, Haddadi *et al.*, 2012, Bharathiveeramani *et al.*, 2012 and Ivanoy *et al.*, 2013).

Table 1. Mean and Range of parents and F₁s for 13 characters in 9 parents diallel cross in maize

S. N.	Characters	Parents			Crosses		
		Mean	Range		Mean	Range	
			Minimum	Maximum		Minimum	Maximum
1	Days to 50% tasseling	88.04	85	90.33	84.89	82.33	88.33
2	Days to 50% silking	91.56	88.66	93.66	88.73	85.66	92.33
3	Days to 75% dry husk	136.37	130.66	139.67	130.75	125.33	138.33
4	Plant height	147.85	140.33	161.34	146.57	130.00	163.33
5	Cob height	71.44	68.66	75.33	69.59	57.66	79.66
6	Cobs/plant	1.16	1.11	1.25	1.15	1.00	1.36
7	Cob weight at 15% moisture	99.86	83.14	121.83	126.42	107.33	152.19
8	No. of grain rows/ cob	13.07	12.11	13.55	13.98	12.88	15.55
9	No. of grains/ row	31.11	27.88	33.98	38.05	32.89	41.33
10	100 grain weight (gm)	20.46	16.76	25.24	19.87	15.63	23.69
11	Grain yield/ cob	82.62	68.84	97.88	105.26	89.02	127.88
12	grain yield/ plant	96.41	84.21	119.21	120.15	99.54	139.79
13	Shelling percentage	82.74	80.45	84.78	83.28	81.27	85.36

Number of Grains per Row

The average number of grains per row among parents varied from 27.88 (KURARA) to 33.98 (TSK 10) where as among crosses it varied from 32.89 (TSK 92 x TSK 27) to 41.33 (TSK 109 x NEW BLUE II). The mean values for the parents and crosses were 31.11 and 38.05, respectively.

100-Grain Weight (g)

The parents and F₁s variability ranged from 16.76 (TSK 109) to 25.24 (KURARA) and 15.63 (TSK 109 x NEW BLUE II) to 23.69 (TSK 27 x HK1-193-1), respectively. The mean values were 20.46 g. and 19.87 g. for parents and F₁s, respectively.

Grain Yield per Cob (g)

The range observed among parents varied from 68.84 (TSK 109) to 97.88 (CIM 78) and among F₁s from 89.02 (HK1-193-1 x NEW BLUE II) to 127.88 (KURARA x NEW BLUE II).

The mean values for parents and F₁s were 82.62 g. and 105.26 g, respectively.

Grain Yield per Plant (g)

The parents and F₁s variability ranged from 84.21 (TSK 109) to 119.21 (CIM 78) g. and 99.54 (HK1-193-1 x NEW BLUE II) to 139.79 (TSK 27 x HK1-193-1) gm., respectively. The mean values were 96.41 g. and 120.15 g. for parents and F₁s, respectively.

Shelling Percentage (%)

The variability for shelling percentage among the parents ranged from 80.45 (CIM 78) to 84.78 (TSK 36). The variability of crosses ranged from 81.27 (CIM 78 x TSK 10) to 85.36 (CIM 78 x TSK 109). The mean values for parents and F₁s were observed 82.74 and 83.28, respectively. Similar findings were also observed by (Ozbas *et al.*, 2004, Singh *et al.*, 2007, Nazeeb *et al.*, 2009, Wannows *et al.*, 2010, Patel *et al.*, 2010, Sumalini *et al.*

al., 2012, Langade *et al.*, 2013, Mohammad *et al.*, 2013, Mustafa *et al.*, 2013, Nayak *et al.*, 2013).

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